

A Prospective Study to Correlate Maternal and Perinatal Outcome with Ophthalmic Artery Doppler Velocimetry in Pre-Eclamptic and Normotensive Patients.

Gita Guin¹, Shweta Sirsikar², Arti Kumari³

¹MS (Obstetrics & Gynaecology), MBBS, LLB, Dean & Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur (M. P.) MS (Obstetrics & Gynaecology).

²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur (M. P.)

³MBBS, Post Graduate Student, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur (M. P.)

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Shweta Sirsikar

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hypertension is one of the most common clinical complications during pregnancy, complicating 6-10% of all pregnancies. Ophthalmic artery provides an accessible window for easy monitoring of maternal cardiovascular changes especially in pregnancy complicated hypertension cases.

Aims and Objectives: To correlate maternal and perinatal outcome with the Ophthalmic Artery Doppler (OAD) parameters observed in the Pre-eclamptic subjects with those observed in Normotensive subjects.

Material and Methods: A prospective case-control study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur, in 126 pregnant subjects (63 Pre-eclamptic patients and 63 Normotensive pregnant controls) in their 2nd and 3rd trimester. They underwent serial OAD velocimetry between 20 weeks to term at three different points of time. OAD parameters, such as Pulsatility Index, Resistance Index, Peak Systolic Velocity, Peak Diastolic Velocity, End Diastolic Velocity and Peak Ratio were measured on transorbital triplex ultrasound scan with 10 MHz linear transducer. These parameters were correlated with maternal and perinatal outcomes. $P < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

Results: Pulsatility Index and Resistance Index were significantly reduced and Peak Ratio was significantly higher in the Pre-eclamptic subjects than the Normotensive subjects. Maternal and perinatal complications were statistically significantly more frequent in subjects with OAD changes rather than those who were hypertensive without OAD changes or were normotensive.

Conclusion: Ophthalmic Artery Doppler velocimetry, in conjunction with other parameters for monitoring maternal and perinatal wellbeing, can be a useful predictor of pregnancy outcome when used accurately and judiciously.

Keywords: Ophthalmic Artery, Hemodynamic Changes, Doppler Parameters, Preeclampsia.

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Introduction

Hypertension is one of the most common clinical complications during pregnancy [1]. It complicates 6-10% of all pregnancies [2]. Among the hypertensive disorders affecting pregnancy, preeclampsia has been a major cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide [3]. It is a pregnancy related hypertensive disorder occurring usually after 20 weeks of gestational age. Preeclampsia causes complications in 3-8% of pregnancies [4]. Overall, 10-15% of maternal deaths are directly associated with preeclampsia and eclampsia [5]. The disease involves multiple organs (liver, kidneys, lungs, brain and the

circulatory system), may cause coagulation disorders and liver malfunction [6]. For the newborns, the risks include intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR) and prematurity. Neurological events, such as intracranial hemorrhage and eclampsia (the pathognomonic conclusive endpoint of preeclampsia), are some of the more frequent means by which preeclampsia causes maternal deaths [7] along with hepatic rupture and acute pulmonary edema. In addition to mortality, preeclampsia is associated with significant short and long term maternal morbidity [8].

There is an increasing awareness of the potential value of assessing maternal hemodynamics and vascular beds outside the uteroplacental unit [9], both as an alternative means for predicting preeclampsia and as an adjunct to the assessment of women with established disease. Ophthalmic artery provides an accessible window for easy monitoring of maternal cardiovascular changes especially in pregnancy complicated hypertension cases. The ophthalmic artery has anatomical continuity [10] with the intracerebral circulation, being a direct branch of the internal carotid artery and is a part of the shunt between the internal and external carotid arteries. Given the embryological, anatomical and functional similarities between the ophthalmic artery and the less accessible intracranial vasculature, cerebrovascular hemodynamics [11] are thought to be reflected directly in Doppler parameters of this vessel. The Ophthalmic Artery Doppler indices have constant reference ranges throughout pregnancy trimesters. Ophthalmic Artery Doppler ultrasound is important tool that can be used to detect hemodynamic changes in preeclampsia and monitor its severity. It is a simple, accurate and objective technique with a predictive value for the development of early-onset preeclampsia equivalent to that of Uterine Artery Doppler evaluation.

This study aimed to correlate maternal-perinatal outcome with the Ophthalmic Artery Doppler indices observed in the Pre-eclamptic subjects with those observed in Normotensive subjects.

Aims & Objectives

1. To study Ophthalmic Artery Doppler velocimetry parameters in randomly selected Pre-eclamptic and normotensive subjects.
2. To prospectively follow normotensive subjects with abnormal Ophthalmic Artery Doppler velocimetry parameters to find the predictive value in Pre-eclampsia.
3. To prospectively evaluate evolving changes in Ophthalmic Artery Doppler and correlate it with maternal- perinatal outcome in Pre-eclampsia

Material and Methods

This prospective case-control study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur, and included 126 participants (63 Pre-eclamptic patients and 63 Normotensive pregnant controls) in their 2nd and 3rd trimester from 1st March 2018 to 31st August 2019, who have normal or elevated blood pressure at the time of antenatal visit.

Inclusion Criteria: All pregnant women in their 2nd and 3rd trimester (gestation period 20 weeks till term) who have normal or elevated blood pressure

at the time of antenatal visit and who are randomly recruited to the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Multiple pregnancies, molar pregnancy, congenital fetal malformation.
- History of diabetes or chronic hypertension or cardiac disorder.
- History of ocular disease.
- Patients on medication for hypertension or on corticosteroids.
- Vasculitis or other vascular diseases that may affect Doppler measurements.
- Patients who don't give consent to be involved in the study.

Procedure Planned:

All antenatal subjects fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criterias were randomly selected, explained high risk related to disease, counseled for participation in study and informed consent was taken. All the routine workup was done along with ophthalmic artery Doppler. Blood pressure was recorded at each antenatal visit and the need for antihypertensive drug decided according to the blood pressure and other symptoms. Subjects with preeclampsia who met the inclusion criteria and consented to the study were recruited as cases and consenting normotensive pregnant subjects were recruited as controls. The subjects underwent serial Ophthalmic Artery Doppler velocimetry between 20 weeks to term (40 weeks) at three different points of time (between 22-27 weeks, then again between 28-33 weeks and subsequently 34-40 weeks).

A General Electric Logiq P5 ultrasound unit with a 10 MHz linear transducer was used to scan the orbit, and OAD parameters were documented. The patient was placed in a supine position with a slight lateral left turn, in accordance with the technique described by Liebet al[12]. Both eyes were closed, and after a resting period of 10 minutes, a small amount of acoustic gel was applied on the upper eyelid. The transducer was then gently placed horizontally over the upper eyelid, and then tilted upward and downward until the ophthalmic artery was identified using color Doppler flow imaging. Both ophthalmic arteries were insonated, the right before the left. Flow velocity was measured approximately 15 mm from the optic disc on the medial side of the optic nerve. After recording six consecutive spectral waveforms of similar size and shape, measurements were made on three waveforms. The PI, RI, PSV, PDV, and EDV were measured on each of the three waveforms and an average value from the three measurements was obtained for each parameter. The PSV was the fastest velocity of blood flow in systole, while the EDV was the slowest recorded velocity of blood

flow in the diastolic phase of the cardiac cycle. All indices with the exception of the peak ratio were either automatically calculated by the ultrasound equipment or manually estimated by tracing the spectral waveform. The peak ratio was manually calculated as the ratio of the values for the PDV (measured by manual tracing of the spectral waveform at the peak after the protodiastolic notch) and the initial peak (i.e. PSV); peak ratio=PDV/PSV or P2/P1. Throughout the examination, care was taken to avoid excessive

compression of the eyelid with the transducer. The angle of insonation was kept below 20°, while the filter was set at 50 Hz, the pulse repetition frequency was set at 125 kHz, and the Doppler sample volume was adjusted to 2 mm. All patients in the case and control group were scanned during the third trimester, and all the OAD velocimetry indices (PSV, EDV, PDV, RI, PI, and peak ratio) were also measured sonographically and recorded (Fig. 1 & 2).

Figure 1: Normotensive Patient Ophthalmic Artery Doppler

Figure 2: Preeclamptic Patient Ophthalmic Artery Doppler

To evaluate maternal outcome (dependent variables), the following complications were considered: HELLP syndrome (microangiopathic hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes and low platelet count), decreased urine output (oliguria – hourly diuresis 30 ml/hr), respiratory distress (acute pulmonary edema-presence of maternal respiratory distress with fine crepitations detected at pulmonary auscultation requiring the use of diuretics), eclampsia (the occurrence of a convulsion in women without prior history) and acute renal failure (presence of oliguria associated

with an acute increase in urea and creatinine levels).

The following variables pertaining to neonates were recorded: Gestational age at birth, Birth weight, Apgar score (at 1 and 5 minutes), need for admission in intensive care unit, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, evidence of various organ dysfunctions associated with perinatal asphyxia like renal, hematological, lung, liver, and cardiac dysfunction, neonatal seizures, mortality before discharge from the hospital. Neonates were classified as Small for gestational age if the birth

weights were less than 10 percentile for that gestational age.

Results and Discussion

Preeclampsia is a major cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. Preeclampsia has been called the disease of theories because of its enigmatic pathophysiology. Its successful prevention depends on accurate prediction of onset and progression. Ophthalmic Artery Doppler Ultrasonography is an important non-invasive tool to quantify perfusion of the ophthalmic artery in pregnant women. [12]

A total of 126 randomly selected subjects were included in the study, out of which 63 subjects are normotensive and 63 are pre-eclamptic subjects. In the present study, preeclampsia was most frequent in younger women, 21-25 years (51.6%) and 2nd most common age group is between 26-30 years (29.4%). Our results were comparable with the study conducted by Onaranet al [13].

The incidence of preeclampsia reduced as the educational status of the subjects improved. Majority of the subjects were educated up to middle school (26.2%) and high school (24.2%).

63 out of 126 subjects (50%) were primigravida. 33(52.4%) out of 63 preeclamptic subjects were primigravida. Similar results were obtained in the study by Manjusha Sajithet al [14] where 53.8% were primigravida.

Average mean arterial pressure (MAP) in normotensive group was 86mmHg in women with 20-27weeks of gestation, 94mmHg in women between 28-33weeks of gestation and 97mmHg in women between 34 weeks to term period. In the preeclampsia group, average MAP was 109mmHg in women with 20-27weeks of gestation, 110mmHg in women between 28-33weeks of gestation and 111mmHg in women between 34 weeks to term period. In severe preeclampsia group, average MAP was 127mmHg in women between 28-33weeks of gestation and 134mmHg in women between 34 weeks to term period. The mean arterial pressure in preeclampsia and severe preeclampsia is higher than that of the normotensive group. Our findings are comparable with the study done by Onaranet al.[13] where the mean arterial pressure in preeclampsia is significantly higher than that of normal pregnancy. They concluded that the mean systolic blood pressure in preeclamptic women(145-163mmHg) and mean diastolic blood pressure(96-116mmHg) is higher than that of mean systolic blood pressure(92-118mmHg) and mean diastolic blood pressure(58-81mmHg) of normotensive women. Subjects with 28-40 weeks mostly presented with severe preeclampsia as compared to subjects diagnosed before 28 weeks which is in keeping with the progressive nature of the disease.

In our study, the Ophthalmic Artery Pulsatility Index and Resistance Index are significantly lower ($p<0.0001$) and Peak Ratio was significantly higher ($p<0.0001$) in Pre-eclamptic than Normotensive subjects. The Pulsatility Index (1.81 ± 0.4) in preeclampsia was lower than that (2.01 ± 0.27) in normotensive subjects. Our results were comparable with the study done by Hata Tet al.[15] (1995) which compared the Ophthalmic Artery Pulsatility Index values from normal pregnant women with those from pre-eclamptic patient. They described that the Pulsatility Index (1.58 ± 0.47) in mild preeclampsia was significantly lower ($P<0.0001$) than that (2.75 ± 0.6) in normotensive pregnant women. They concluded that mild preeclampsia was associated with a significant decrease in ophthalmic artery vascular resistance, whereas ophthalmic artery vascular resistance in severe preeclampsia increased as the disease process advanced.

Similar results were also found in study done by Riskin-Mashiah S et al [16], where the cerebral arteries pulsatility and resistive indices were lower in women with preeclampsia compared with pregnant women who were normotensive. Both PI and RI are decreased in patients of pre-eclamptic groups compared to that in normal pregnancy group due to the effect of vasodilatation and orbital hyperperfusion in preeclampsia. Ayazet al [17] found that both PI and RI were significantly lower in the ophthalmic arteries of mild-moderately preeclamptic women than normotensive women at similar stage of pregnancy. They concluded that in patient with mild-moderate preeclampsia, Ophthalmic Artery Doppler ultrasonography detects hemodynamic changes that are not present in normotensive gravid women. Reversal of Doppler patterns with progressive disease supports the hypothesis suggesting the presence of early vasodilatation and late vasospasm in the etiology of preeclampsia.

In the present study, Resistance Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index(PI) decreased as the mean arterial pressure increased. Similar results were obtained in study done by Hata T, Hata K, Moritake K [18] (1997), who too compared maternal ophthalmic artery pulsatility index values in normotensive pregnancies and pregnancies complicated by hypertensive disorders. The Pulsatility Index inversely correlated well with the mean arterial blood pressure. The results suggest that the lower Pulsatility Index should be interpreted as orbital vascular vasodilatation, indicating orbital hyperperfusion or hyperemia. Changes in Pulsatility Index in the ophthalmic artery may be indicative of similar changes in other cerebral vessels.

The Resistivity Index of ophthalmic artery showed an inverse correlation with mean arterial pressure

of pregnant women. Our findings were comparable with the study done by Ayazet al [17] and Diniz et al [19]. Diniz et al [19] concluded that orbital vascular impedance reduction with orbital hyperperfusion was present in severe pre-eclamptic women compared to normotensive pregnant women.

Similar study by Olatunji et al [20] concluded that Resistivity Index and Pulsatility Index were reduced in preeclamptic group when compared with healthy pregnant women and peak ratio was significantly higher in the preeclamptic group supporting the hyperperfusion model of altered central hemodynamics in this group of pregnant women.

Likewise, Cristiane Alves de Oliveira et al [21] found the mean \pm SDs for the Resistivity Index, Pulsatility Index and Peak Ratio in women with severe preeclampsia were 0.63 ± 0.09 , 1.13 ± 0.31 and 0.89 ± 0.12 , respectively, as against means of 0.75 ± 0.05 , 1.88 ± 0.43 and 0.52 ± 0.1 . They concluded that Doppler imaging of ophthalmic artery showed central overperfusion among pregnant women with severe preeclampsia. Similarly, Oliveria CA et al [22] also found decrease in the Pulsatility Index values with advancing gestational age.

RI values below 0.61 suggest progression to severe preeclampsia. This is similar to the cutoff value of 0.657 (sensitivity 73.3%, specificity 88.8%) defined by de Oliveira et al [22] in their Brazilian population. It is also consistent with the finding of Barbosa et al²³ who investigated the association between OARI and clinical evidence of posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES) in patients with severe preeclampsia and found that patients with severe preeclampsia who had symptoms of PRES presented lower OARI ($p < 0.0001$) and higher mean blood pressure at admission. As in these studies, in our study also those with RI of 0.6 were complicated by eclampsia. [23]

Our study included 126 subjects who were evaluated by Ophthalmic Artery Doppler between 22-27 weeks, then again at 28-33 weeks and subsequently 34-40 weeks. A total of 23 out of 126 subjects had positive OADV changes at the first visit. Of them 20 were put on antihypertensive treatment while the blood pressure of the remainder 3 subjects was within normal limits. At the second visit, the same 23 subjects had a deterioration of the values of RI, PI and PR. At this visit, a total of 38 subjects were put on antihypertensive treatment even though the OADV of 15 subjects whose BP was raised was normal. At the third visit, similarly, no additional subjects required antihypertensive treatment other than the previous 38 subjects. Only 2 of the total of 23 subjects with positive and

deteriorating (RI=0.6) OADV changes developed eclampsia while the remainder 21 did not have eclampsia. None of those who had normal OADV developed eclampsia even though they needed antihypertensive changes.

Similarly, only 2 of the total of 23 subjects with positive and deteriorating OADV changes developed pulmonary edema and only 1 of the total of 23 subjects with positive and deteriorating OADV changes developed HELLP syndrome, one other had acute renal failure and 2 had abruption. Only 1 normotensive subject without OADV developed abruption.

A total of 14 babies were small for gestational age, of them 4 were born to mothers who were normotensive, 2 were born to mothers who were on antihypertensive but had normal OADV and 8 were born to mothers who had abnormal OADV and were on antihypertensives. It can therefore be postulated that abnormal OADV is associated with a greater likelihood of having small for gestational age babies.

4 subjects on antihypertensive treatment with positive and deteriorating OADV delivered babies having Apgar score < 7 at 5 minutes, while 2 newborns of subjects with normal OADV on antihypertensive treatment had Apgar < 7 at 5 minutes. 3 subjects who were normotensive and had normal OADV had newborns having Apgar score < 7 at 5 minutes.

3 newborns each of all the three groups had hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy and required NICU admission. Intra uterine fetal demise occurred in the two pregnancies that were complicated by eclampsia. It may therefore be postulated that other than small for gestational age which was more frequent in subjects with abnormal OADV on anti-hypertensive treatment, other neonatal complications could not be predicted with certainty by the presence or absence of abnormal OADV. All that mattered was that they were on antihypertensive treatment. The IUFDs were a consequence of eclampsia which was restricted to subjects with abnormal OADV on antihypertensive treatment.

Summary

Hypertension is one of the most common causes of maternal morbidity and mortality. Among the hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, preeclampsia is the major cause of maternal morbidity, mortality, perinatal death, prematurity and intrauterine growth retardation. So the identification of high risk pregnancies at an early stage can help to prevent the complications and should encourage intensive therapy aimed at saving the life of the mother and the fetus. This will have a great impact in reduction of maternal and perinatal mortality.

Analysis of the Ophthalmic Artery Doppler velocimetry of the pregnant women is a non invasive and safe procedure. It is painless, repeatable and can be done at the same sitting as obstetric ultrasonography. Ophthalmic Artery Sonography is well tolerated by patients and does not take long time to perform. Given the embryological, anatomical and functional similarities between the ophthalmic artery and the less accessible intracranial vasculature, cerebral hemodynamics are thought to be directly reflected in the vessel's Doppler parameters.

In our study, we enrolled a total of 126 randomly selected subjects out of which 63 are normotensive and 63 are pre-eclamptic subjects who underwent ophthalmic artery Doppler velocimetry between 20 weeks to term (40 weeks) at three different points of time and the Doppler indices were correlated with maternal and perinatal outcome.

The following observations were made:

1. Preeclampsia was most frequent in younger women, 21-25 years (51.6%) and 2nd most common age group is between 26-30 years (29.4%).
2. Most subjects were educated upto middle school (26.2%) and high school (24.2%).
3. 33 (52.4%) out of 63 preeclamptic subjects were primigravida.
4. The Ophthalmic Artery Pulsatility Index and Resistance Index are significantly reduced ($p < 0.0001$) and Peak Ratio was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) in the preeclamptic subjects than the normotensive subjects.
5. PI and RI are decreased in pre-eclamptic groups compared to that in normotensive group due to effect of vasodilatation and orbital hyperperfusion in preeclampsia.
6. PI and RI decreased as the mean arterial pressure increased. Patients with RI of 0.6 were complicated by eclampsia.
7. Only 2 of the total of 23 subjects with positive and deteriorating ($RI = 0.6$) OADV changes developed eclampsia while the remainder 21 did not have eclampsia. None of those who had normal OADV developed eclampsia even though they needed antihypertensive changes.
8. Maternal complications were more frequent in subjects with OADV changes rather than those who were hypertensive without OADV changes or were normotensive. Only 1 normotensive subject without OADV changes developed abortion.
9. A total of 14 babies were small for gestational age, of them 4 were born to mothers who were normotensive, 2 were born to mothers who were on anti-hypertensive but had normal OADV but a significantly large number i.e. 8 were born to mothers who had abnormal OADV and were on antihypertensives.

10. The two intra uterine fetal deaths occurred in the two patients who progressed to eclampsia with abnormal OADV parameters. This significantly worsened the perinatal outcome of subjects with positive OADV changes as compared to those who had no OADV changes.

Conclusion

The Ophthalmic Artery Pulsatility Index and Resistive Index were reduced and the Peak Ratio was increased in the pre-eclamptic subjects compared with the normotensive subjects supporting the hyperperfusion model of altered cerebral hemodynamics in this group of pregnant women. Maternal and perinatal outcome was worse in the subjects having reduced impedance indices (RI and PI) and increased Peak Ratio and on antihypertensive drugs. We postulate that the Ophthalmic Artery Doppler velocimetry can be used in deciding whether pregnancies complicated by raised blood pressure remote from the period of fetal survival in a given setup can be managed conservatively or such pregnancies be terminated. Hence, Ophthalmic Artery Doppler velocimetry, in conjunction with other parameters for monitoring maternal and perinatal wellbeing, can become a useful predictor of pregnancy outcome when used accurately and judiciously. If the findings are endorsed by larger studies, then the information can also be used for optimal patient counselling and in medico-legal conflicts.

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Conflict of Interest: NONE DECLARED

References

1. Hypertension in Pregnancy, Task force Guidelines, ACOG.
2. Wagner SJ, Barac S, Garovic VD. Hypertensive pregnancy disorders: current concepts. *J Clin Hypertens* 2007;9:560.
3. Maltarf, Sibai. BM. Eclampsia VIII. Risk factors for maternal morbidity. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2000 Feb. 182(2):307-12.
4. Dolea C, AbouZahr C. Global burden of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in the year 2000. GBD2000 Working paper. World Health Organisation: Geneva, 2003.
5. Duley L. The global impact of pre-eclampsia and eclampsia. *Semin Perinatol* 2009;33:130-137.
6. Gibson P, Carson M. Hypertension and pregnancy. *E Medicine*, 2006;1.
7. MacKay AP, Berg CJ, Atrash HK. Pregnancy-related mortality from pre-eclampsia and eclampsia. *Obstet Gynecol* 2001;97:533-538.
8. Bellamy L, Casas JP, Hingorani AD, Williams DJ. Preeclampsia and risk of cardiovascular disease and cancer in later life: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ* 2007;335:974.

9. Kane SC, Dennis AT. Doppler assessment of uterine blood flow in preeclampsia: A review. *Hypertens Pregnancy*. 2015; 34:400-421.
10. Ayaz T, Akansel G, Hayirlioglu A, Arslan A, Suer N, Kuru I. Ophthalmic artery color Doppler ultrasonography in mild-to-moderate preeclampsia. *Eur J Radiol*. 2003; 46: 244-9.
11. Jaffe G, Schatz H. Ocular manifestations of preeclampsia. *Am J Ophthalmol*. 1987; 103:309-315.
12. Lieb WE, Cohen SM, Merton DA, Shields JA, Mitchell DG, Goldberg BB. Color Doppler imaging of the eye and orbit. *Arch Ophthalmol*. 1991; 103:527-531.
13. Zafer Onaran, Yasem, Karaden Yilmazbas, Retrobulbar Hemodynamics in Pregnancy *Gazi Med j*. 2012; 23: 55-8.
14. Manjushasajith, Vandana Nimbargi, Atmaram Panwar, Amit Modi, Ronak Sumariya, Incidence of Pregnancy Induced hypertension and prescription pattern of antihypertensive drugs in pregnancy *International Journal of Pharma Sciences and Research*. 2014.
15. Hata T, Senoh D, Hata K, Kitao M. Ophthalmic artery velocimetry in pregnant women. *Lancet*. 1992.
16. Riskin-Mashiah S, Belfort MA, Sade GR, Herd AJ. Side-to-side differences in transcranial Doppler parameters in normotensive and preeclamptic pregnant women. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2004; 190:194-8
17. Ayaz T, Akansel G, Hayirlioglu A, Arslan A, Suer N, Kuru I. Ophthalmic artery color Doppler ultrasonography in mild-to-moderate preeclampsia. *Eur J Radiol*. 2003; 46:244-249.
18. Hata T, Hata K, Moritake K. Maternal ophthalmic artery Doppler velocimetry in normotensive pregnancies and pregnancies complicated by hypertensive disorders. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 1997; 177: 174-8
19. Diniz ALD, Moron AF, Santos MC, Sass N, Pires CR, Debs CL. Ophthalmic artery Doppler as a measure of severe preeclampsia. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2008; 100:216-220
20. Richard Busayo Olatunji, Ademola Joseph Adekanmi, Millicent Ohumniwa Obajimi, Olumuyiwa Adebola Roberts and Temitope Olumuyiwa Ojo. Maternal ophthalmic artery Doppler velocimetry in pre-eclampsia in Southwestern Nigeria. Published online 2015 Jul. 20., doi: 10.2147/IJWH.S86314.
21. de Oliveira CA, Moreira de Sa RA, Velarde LG, Marchiori E, Netto HC, Ville Y. Doppler velocimetry of the ophthalmic artery in normal pregnancy; reference values. *J Ultrasound Med*. 2009; 28:563-569.
22. deOliveira CA, Moreira de Sa RA, Velarde LG, da Silva FC, do Vale FA, Netto HC. Change in ophthalmic artery Doppler indices in hypertensive disorders during pregnancy. *J Ultrasound Med*. 2013; 32:609-616.
23. Barbosa AS, Pereira AK, Reis ZSN, Lage EM, Leite HV, Cabral ACV. Ophthalmic artery-resistive index and evidence of over perfusion-related encephalopathy in severe preeclampsia. *Hypertension*. 2010; 55:189-193.